

“Sonic Rhopalia”

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1. PROGRAM NOTES

The Jellyfish is a species with one of the most simplistic and complete Umwelts. Its pulsating movements are caused by a refined network of a few neural receptors, named Rhopalia. In the ocean, these pulses ripple as waves in the water, influencing the organic pulses of the next jellyfish. Such interactions (that cannot be seen by the naked eye), have sustained the existence of the species across 6 billion years.

“Sonic Rhopalia” is an installation that reframes this natural phenomenon as a sound system. The work is produced by the pulsation of four *Aurelia aurita* (a.k.a. moon jellyfish). By using TouchDesigner and a web camera to capture the movement of each jellyfish, we detect its pulse through image analysis (using OpenCV). Once its pulse is detected, it is used as a trigger for music composition, on M4L (Max for Live) through OSC. Sounds are played in response to each pulse, and when synchronized, different chords and rhythms are produced, developing into different phases with varying soundscapes.

By reframing jellyfish as an interface for music generation, Sonic Rhopalia allows the audience to experience the vitality of jellyfish in a completely new dimension from conventional methods of bio-marine appreciation.

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Fig. 1.1. Installation at the ZOU-NO-HANA FUTUREScape PROJECT 2023 in Japan in December 2023 (left)

Fig. 1.2. Installation at the ZOU-NO-HANA FUTUREScape PROJECT 2023 in Japan in December 2023 (right)

2. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

This work is a sound installation that is created by the pulsation (a chance operation,) of jellyfish. The work tracks the movement of four *Aurelia aurita* (a.k.a. moon jellyfish) to create a sonification. The aleatoric soundscape is created by the rhythm of the jellyfish in each respective aquarium, with the synchronization of their pulses creating musical and visual interest throughout the installation.

Regarding the Music Generation System

The music generation system utilizes bangs received on Max for Live through OSC from the pulse-detection model on Touch Designer. Max receives the pulse of the four separate jellyfish, calculates the time elapsed between the pulses, and if the time is under 10ms, sends a bang indicates synchronization. In this way, by using four separate pulse data, and six combinations of pulse synchronization, we propose a music generation system that projects the vitality of the pulsating jellyfish.

The soundscape development takes place through the following three phases:

Phase 1

Sound is designed to express the rhythm of the jellyfish, and its synchronizations in the most simplistic way. Each jellyfish pulse is mapped to a simplistic, mechanical beep of a

synthesizer, which is played simultaneous to the movements through the respective speakers placed below each of the four aquariums. When the pulses of the jellyfish synchronize, a different synth pad chord is played, depending on which jellyfish were in sync.

Phase 2

Retaining the same basic structure as Phase 1, this phase utilizes ambient tones to showcase different approach to expressing the rhythm of the jellyfish, and its interactivity. Another layer of complexity is added as the pulses are used as modulators for the other jellyfish. For example, when jellyfish A pulsates, it triggers a high-cut filter on the sounds of jellyfish B.

Phase 3

The final phase utilizes sonification methods used in Phase 1 and Phase 2, with sound design emphasizing the rhythm of the pulses. In addition to the pulse, the time elapsed between the pulse is mapped to a metronome creating complex polyrhythms.

The musical development of these three phases is determined by the number of times the pulses of the four jellyfish synchronize. One loop consists of 80 synchronizations, where the music develops from simplistic, ambient, to complex over the course of 8-12 minutes (depending on the movement on the jellyfish). The pulses are used as triggers, modulators, and metronome counters, allowing the composer to interpret the rhythms created by the jellyfish from multiple musical standpoints.

Regarding the Jellyfish Pulse Detection and Lighting System

The Pulse Detection and Lighting System is controlled using Touch Designer :

Pulse Detection:

With our current system, a web-camera is used to input real-time video to Touch designer. The jellyfish image is independent from its background, after which its change in area is calculated using OpenCV (an opensource library). The system calculates the difference in area between the current frame, and the previous frame, and determines a pulse when the area increases.

Lighting System:

The DMX lights light up each of the 4 aquariums in sync with the pulses, with varying patterns for pulse and synchronization, and on the musical phase, adding a visual dimension to the work to enhance the experience, also allowing a broader viewpoint. The light ADSR patterns are created on Max and sent to the DMX system through Touch Designer.

Fig. 2.1. System and Software Architecture Diagram

Fig. 3.1. Layout Diagram (left)

Fig. 3.2. Detailed Diagram of Inside the Aquarium Tank / Aquarium Stand (right)

* Specific “Fig. 2.2. Sound System Diagram”, “Fig. 3.3. Cabling Diagram” and “Fig. 3.4. Power Supply Layout Diagram” is attached as supplementary materials.

3. PERFORMANCE NOTES

Table I. Simulation Configuration

Jellyfish	Aurelia aurita ×4
Audio Interface	Input ×8, Output ×8
Active Speaker	×7

LED Par Light	×4
USB Web Cam	Wide Angle Web Cam ×4
PC	Master pc ×1, OS: Windows 11, CPU: Corei7 or more, GPU: VRAM10GB or more, USB A Port: 4 or more, Industrial USB Hub
Storage Box	For Aquarium ×4, For Machine (PC etc.) ×1
Extension cable	×11
Electric wire reel	×3
Dimmer Unit	×1
USB Extender	×4
Cable	XLR♂-TS ×6, XLR ×8, Phone ×2
USB Cable	×2
DMX Cable	×5
LAN Cable	×4
Wi-fi	×1
Aquarium Equipment	Please refer to the Certificate of Research Ethics Approval, provided as supplementary material.

Source: Fig. 1, 2, 3, Certificate of Research Ethics Approval

Note: In general, we plan to ship the required equipment from Japan, but if there is any equipment that we could rent from the exhibition space, we like to utilize the available provisions. Specifically, we would like to loan a computer with the specifications mentioned above. Adding on, if there is a space we could use to store the equipment (e.g. a backyard), we would also like to utilize the space. In regards to specifics on management of the equipment and jellyfish, please refer to the Certificate of Research Ethics Approval, provided as supplementary material.

Space Requirement

A space of depth 8m x width 10m would be most apt for this installation. For the audience to view the installation from both sides of the aquarium, the plan suggests leaving a space of 2m between each aquarium tank. The height is 154.7cm (sum of aquarium tank and stand). Our spatial plan uses measurements from our debut exhibition at the ZOU-NO-HANA FUTUREScape PROJECT 2023 held in December 2023, and we are confident in its feasibility.

In addition, we believe the “Academy Gallery” is best suited for our installation for the following reasons:

1. The space allows for the installation to be exhibited independent of sonic interference from the environmental noise.
2. It would be possible to create a dark room space (which would largely enhance the accuracy of pulse detection).
3. The space fulfills the safety and ethical requirements for exhibiting live jellyfish.

If there are any other spaces that would fulfill our spatial requirements, we are open to considering other options as well.

Floor Plan & Logistical Requirement

The following are logistical requirements as we deemed as necessary exhibition experience at the ZOU-NO-HANA FUTUREScapePROJECT held in December 2023. Firstly, require 10 hours (half a day) for the entire set-up process, and 2 hours for dismantling. We would set up the installation in the following order:

1. Install the aquarium, stands and equipment.
2. Fill tanks with sea water.
3. Installation of machinery, including speakers
4. Installation of wiring and cabling.

Wi-fi would be a requirement for the project, as the installation involves OSC connection. The overall wattage required amounts to 2000W, and we would require 4-6 plug points to ensure a safe and sufficient supply of power. We ensure to put in our best effort, and be flexible in our planning, so please let us know if there are any questions or concerns.

4. MEDIA LINK(S)

·Video : https://youtu.be/HBFbDtB_Nsw

·Audio : <https://00m.in/aGBpc>

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The work has also received supervision from Dr. Sho Toshino, Senior Researcher at the [Kuroshio Biological Research Foundation](#) (Japan).

In case of installation at NIME 2024, we plan on collaborating with Jellyfish Breeding farm, [Jellyfish Farm](#) (Germany) and/or [Jellyfish Concept](#) (France), to work with live jellyfish.

ETHICAL STANDARDS

Throughout the process of research, development, and installation of our project involving live jellyfish, we have worked under the supervision of Dr. Sho Toshino, Senior Researcher at the Kuroshio Biological Research Foundation. Working under his supervision, we ensured that all our research took place under ethical standards, and that the sound and lights do not burden the jellyfish. We have received permission in advance from the Kuroshio Biological Research Foundation regarding lighting and speaker systems, and all other aquarium-related equipment used for the project.

Supplementary Materials:

We have attached the Certificate of Research Ethics Approval, and the Letter of Recommendation as supplementary materials. We have also attached further diagrams on the sound system, cabling and power supply layouts.